

IMPREGNATION AND CONSOLIDATION OF DIFFERENT GF/PP COMMINGLED YARNS

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ABSTRACT

Impregnation mechanisms of different kinds of GF/PP commingled yarns have been studied. As the reinforcing fibres were always the same, a global description has been worked out. The mathematical approach for fibre bed permeability of Gutowski has been applied. Differences in the degree of impregnation after the same process conditions can only be due to different sizes of fibre agglomerations, thus the initial distribution of reinforcing fibres and matrix. The exact distribution of fibres in the intermediate material and after processing was determined by scanning electron microscopy and data given from the material supplier. The importance of different process parameters is weighted by determining the density and mechanical properties of the specimens.

1. INTRODUCTION

Some very helpful basics for impregnation mechanisms have been worked out by Kozeny and Carman [1] and Gutowski [2]. Their constants obtained for fibre bed permeabilities are only dependent on the characteristics and orientation of the reinforcing fibres. This means that it should be possible to derive a model for a large amount of different intermediate material forms, as long as the reinforcing fibre remains the same. Bijsterbosch [3] has studied impregnation in a thermoplastic bath and gives helpful indications for modelling. Studies about impregnation and compaction behaviour of intermediate thermoplastic matrix composites have already been done by Van West [4], Hamada [5], Kim [6], and Ye [7] but the assumption to characterize the material and the impregnation behaviour were quite global. Vodermyer [8] showed that impregnation times can be very short if a homogenous mixing of fibres and matrix is given. It is also known from continuous processes such as filament winding, pultrusion and double belt pressing that there is no need for long processing times. It seems therefore evident to design a discontinuous hot pressing process which allows to simulate the conditions of continuous processes. The problem of studying the impregnation behaviour of thermoplastics is, that the polymer is liquid only at elevated temperatures. This means that the material has to be heated up to a defined temperature, with the problem that impregnation may already start during the heating-up phase within which it cannot be controlled directly. In the present work, a more detailed characterization, especially concerning the quality of impregnation as a function of pressure dependent fibre volume fraction and size of fibre agglomerations has been worked out. Also a process has been applied which permits to define the impregnation time better than known from previous approaches.

2. MATERIALS

Different glass fibre (GF) / polypropylene (PP) commingled yarns were supplied by Vetrotex, France. The exact specifications are listed in Table 1. Details, about calculations of agglomeration sizes and initial void contents, can be checked in [9]. The viscosity of PP, measured by capillar

rheometry at Vetrotex [10] and by parallel plate rheometry at IVW, Kaiserslautern, resulted in the following viscosities:

$$\eta_{(T=175^{\circ}\text{C})} = 700 \text{ Pas}, \eta_{(T=185^{\circ}\text{C})} = 530 \text{ Pas}, \eta_{(T=195^{\circ}\text{C})} = 410 \text{ Pas}.$$

Table 1. Specifications of materials used

Material Properties	Standard	Variation 2	Variation 3	Variation 4	Variation 6
Tex of bundle	800	800	1330	460	800
Tex of glass fibres GF	320	320	1330	320	320
Volume fraction of GF, V_g	0.19	0.19	0.19	0.45	0.19
Densities:					
Glass, ρ_g [g/cm ³]	2.56	2.56	2.56	2.56	2.56
PP, ρ_{pp} [g/cm ³]	0.906	0.906	0.906	0.906	0.906
Melting Temperature of PP, T_m [°C]	165	165	165	165	165
Radius of fibres:					
Glass, r_{fg} [µm]	7	7	8.5	7	7
PP, r_{pp} [µm]	10	10	10	10	10
Melt flow index, MFI	20	20	20	20	55
Mingling quality	good	poor	good	good	good
Radius of GF agglomeration, r_o [µm]	90 - 100	150 - 200	100	150 - 200	as standard
Number of agglomerations in one bundle, n	7.96	2.6	13.2	2.6	as standard
Area of:					
GF, A_{gf} [mm ²]	0.125	0.125	0.207	0.125	"
Voids, A_{vo} [mm ²]	0.125	0.125	0.207	0.125	"
Polymer, A_{pp} [mm ²]	0.53	0.53	0.883	0.155	"
Totally compacted bundle, A_t [mm ²]	0.665	0.665	1.09	0.280	"
incl. voids between GF, $A_{t,v}$ [mm ²]	0.78	0.78	1.297	0.405	"
Initial void content, X_{vo}	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.31	"

* bold letters signalise the differences to the standard material

3. DETERMINATION OF THE STATE OF IMPREGNATION AND CONSOLIDATION

3.1 MANUFACTURING OF THE GF/PP LAMINATES

The layers of unidirectional "prepreg" sheets were manufactured by winding individual yarn onto an aluminum plate, with subsequent two lines welding of the yarn at both ends. Consolidation of the laminates was performed by using a small steel mould with a cavity of 80x100 mm² and a laboratory heat press. The cold and filled mould was put into the already heated press and set under slight pressure, just to assure sufficient contact for heat transfer. The temperature was controlled by a thermocouple some millimeters below the cavity in order to ensure a reliable cavity temperature signal. When the processing temperature was reached, the whole pressure was applied immediately. From then on the time of impregnation was measured. The final laminate thickness was about 3 mm.

The following parameters have been varied:

temperature : 155-195°C, pressure: 0.38-3MPa, time: 0.5-10min, with a const. cooling rate of 17 °C/min.

3.2 VOID CONTENT AND PRESSURE DEPENDENT GLASS FIBRE CONTENT

The void content was determined by density measurements. The laminate density, ρ_l , under different processing conditions was determined according to ASTM-792. The theoretical density, ρ_t , was determined by burning off the matrix in order to obtain the real glass fibre content. The apparent void content, X_v , was then determined by:

$$X_v = \frac{\rho_t - \rho_l}{\rho_t} \quad (1)$$

The void content, taken as one characteristic of the consolidation status, was used to define optimum processing conditions. The samples were cross-sectioned perpendicular to the fibre direction, then polished, and ultra-sonically cleaned. With the help of scanning electron microscopy (SEM) fibre volume fractions in the glass fibre agglomeration as a function of pressure have been determined. This was carried out by directly image analysing the SEM-screen. The results were calculated from the average of 5 to 10 different locations on each specimen.

3.3 MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION

Characterization of mechanical properties as a function of impregnation conditions was carried out by a small 3-point bending facility for the determination of transverse elastic modulus, according to DIN 53 457, and a shear test facility, being developed by Lauke [11] (Figure 1). The length of the span for the bending test amounted to 40 mm, the width and thickness of the specimens were 10 mm and 3 mm, respectively. The cross head speed was chosen to be 1 mm/min. The specimens for the shear test were 10 mm wide, 6 to 7 mm high, and 3 mm thick. For both tests an average value was calculated out of 5 specimens.

Figure 1. Shear facility

4. MATHEMATICAL APPROACH TO IMPREGNATION AND CONSOLIDATION

The flow of a liquid through a porous bed is generally described by Darcy's law

$$\dot{q} = \frac{dz}{dt} = -\frac{K_p}{\eta} \frac{dp}{dz} \quad (2)$$

where

\dot{q} : rate of penetration

p : pressure

η : viscosity

z : penetration distance

K_p : permeability

Integrating Eqn (2) twice and assuming that K_p is independent of the applied pressure p_a (which is not a true assumption), leads to an impregnation time

$$\Delta t = \frac{\eta z^2}{2K_p (p_a - p_o)} \quad (3)$$

where

p_o : atmospheric pressure

p_a : applied pressure

For higher fibre volume fractions Gutowski et al [2] found a relationship for radial flow, which differs from the Kozeny-Carman approach [1]:

$$K_{p,G} = \frac{r_{fg}^2 \sqrt{\frac{V_a}{V_f} - 1}}{4k_{zz} \left(\frac{V_a}{V_f} + 1\right)} \quad (4)$$

where

V_f : pressure dependent glass fibre volume fraction in a fibre agglomeration

k_{zz} : Gutowski constant for permeability

r_{fg} : radius of glass fibres

Following Gutowski, the relationship between applied pressure and fibre volume fraction can be described by

$$\Delta p = p_a - p_o = A_s \frac{\sqrt{\frac{V_f}{V_o} - 1}}{\left(\frac{V_a}{V_f} - 1\right)^4} \quad (5)$$

where

V_o : fibre volume fraction at atmospheric pressure (0.68), determined by SEM

V_a : max. fibre volume fraction (0.83) [2]

A_s : elastic constant of the fibre bed.

Figure 2. Comparison of p - V_f relationship determined by means of SEM and image analysis with the Gutowski approach for well and poorly aligned fibre beds, $A_s = 53$ Pa and $A_s = 287$ Pa, respectively

A_s depends linearly on the bending modulus and the degree of alignment or waviness of the reinforcing fibres. Gutowski [2] has determined A_s to be 160 Pa for a well aligned and 860 Pa for a poorly aligned carbon fibre bed. The modulus of glass fibres is just a third of carbon fibres, so that it can be assumed that A_s is also a third, which means 53 and 287 Pa for well and poorly aligned glass fibre beds, respectively. Figure 2 compares the measured fibre volume fraction with the two different assumptions of fibre bed alignment. For the well aligned case the model

approaches the experimental data quite well. Another unknown parameter of Eqn (3) is the penetration distance z after different impregnation times. z can then be expressed by means of the measured void content X_v :

$$X_v = \frac{\pi n(r_o - z)^2(1 - V_f)}{A_t} \quad (6)$$

$$z = r_o - \sqrt{\frac{X_v A_t}{\pi n(1 - V_f)}} \quad (6a)$$

Figure 3 illustrates the flow into the agglomeration. Combining Eqns (3), (4), and (6a) the impregnation time can be expressed by

$$t_{X_v, G} = \frac{2\eta k_{zz} (r_o - \sqrt{\frac{X_v A_t}{(1 - V_f)\pi n}})^2 (\frac{V_a}{V_f} + 1)}{r_{fg}^2 (P_a - P_o) \sqrt{\frac{V_a}{V_f} - 1}} \quad (7)$$

For r_o , r_{fg} , A_t , and n see Table 1 and Figure 3.

k_{zz} can now be estimated for several process conditions and material variations. It has to be a constant and should be the same for other matrices. With these equations it appears very clearly that the crucial variable to be measured is the void content. As, however, relevant small void contents between 0 and 10% are very difficult to measure, it becomes evident that the k_{zz} -value obtained in such a method must have high standard deviations. Furthermore, impregnation times are rather short (in the order of a few minutes), and it is therefore of high importance to know in which order time, pressure, and temperature determine the desired quality of impregnation. In order to eliminate the effect of heating and cooling, a specimen, which has only been heated up and cooled down was processed as a kind of reference.

Figure 3. Schematic of assumed impregnation mechanism, fibre bundle with $n = 3$ agglomerations

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 VOID CONTENT

Figure 4 illustrates the void content as a function of pressure for different temperatures and material variations. The influence of temperature is most significant from below the polymer melting point up to 175 °C, whereas a further increase in temperature only results in a slight void reduction. It can clearly be seen that already low increases in pressure are very helpful in comparison to atmospheric pressure, but that pressure differences beyond 1 or 2 MPa only slightly reduce the void content further. This is confirmed by the microscopical observations.

Figure 4. Void content as a function of temperature and pressure

5.2 MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION

Maximum shear strengths reached are about 23 MPa. For each material most improvement is made by a pressure increase from zero to 1 MPa (Figure 5a) and, for the standard material, by a temperature increase from 155 °C to 185 °C. This strong temperature influence is considered to be the same for all material variations. Similar results and trends for this material were obtained in filament winding at the IVW. Figure 5b shows the flexural modulus for the materials after processing at 180/185 °C. The main increase, here again, can be observed between atmospheric pressure and 1 MPa.

Maximum shear strength is governed by matrix properties and should therefore be independent on the amount of reinforcing fibres, that means it should be the same for all material variations. But fibre reinforcement can weaken these properties if the fibre / matrix bonding is incomplete. With increasing fibre content the probability of unbonded fibres increases. Materials with a higher fibre content are therefore more sensitive to changes in processing conditions for properties perpendicular to the fibres. In the present case this was expected for variation 4. The transverse modulus, in contrast, has to be higher for a material with a higher fibre content.

Pressure enforces the polymer flow through the glass fibre bundles. Higher pressures, of course, still increase the enforced flow, but, on the other hand compact the fibre bed and therefore diminish its permeability. The second effect seems to become rather important for pressures beyond 2 MPa.

Figure 5. a) Shear strength and b) transverse flexural modulus of several material variations, consolidation time $t = 1$ min

5.3 DETERMINATION OF OPTIMUM PROCESSING CONDITIONS

Figure 6 shows the process window using the microscopically determined and the Gutowski Δp - V_f relationship. This comparison clarifies the importance of fibre volume fraction for impregnation. Differences of about 3% between measured and calculated fibre volume content (Figure 4) result in differences of up to 30% in impregnation times. The Gutoŵski permeability describes well the impregnation behaviour of variation 2 and 4, but calculates too short times for the standard material. Modelling the impregnation of the standard material was the most difficult, as impregnation times are short, void contents low, and thus the relative error of experimentally obtained results higher than for the other variations. The authors impression is, that the Gutowski model still overweighs the influence of pressure increase at higher pressures. A pressure increase beyond 2 or 3 MPa does not shorten impregnation times or improve the quality of the specimens very much.

Figure 6. Processing window for GF/PP commingled yarns; comparison of material variations and of microscopically obtained and calculated Δp - V_f relationship

k_{zz} of Figure 6 has been calculated from applied impregnation times and corresponding void contents by Eqn (6) in paragraph 4; it amounts to about 5. With this k -value impregnation times have been recalculated from the given void content. The times agree rather well with the holding times for variations 2 and 4, especially for lower pressures and void contents of about 5%. For almost void free specimens, obtained by higher pressures and longer holding times, the calculated times are shorter than those of the experiments.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The impregnation behaviour of several GF/PP commingled yarns has been studied. The penetration distance was expressed by the measured void content of the specimens. The Gutowski approach for permeability has been applied to predict impregnation times for given pressures and temperatures. It was possible to describe different material variations with the same approach.

Very crucial for impregnation conditions are the geometrical arrangement of the reinforcing fibres, the determination of impregnation time and of the remaining void content. The influence of heating up and cooling down is certainly not negligible. Specimens, processed at atmospheric pressure served as references for the initial situation of impregnation.

Main improvement of impregnation and compaction quality is obtained by applying low pressures up to 2 MPa. The size of fibre agglomeration governs the impregnation time in a very important

manner. Impregnation times of the materials studied were in the range of a few minutes to obtain void contents below 2% and are close to those in continuous processes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Thanks are due to Vetrotex, Chambéry, France, who kindly supplied the testing materials. Further thanks are addressed to the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) and the Korean Science and Engineering Foundation (KOSEF) for the support of this work within the scope of the German-Korean Collaboration Project (DFG-FR-675/11-2). Professor Friedrich is grateful for the financial assistance from the Fonds der Chemischen Industrie, Frankfurt, for his personal research activities in 1995.

REFERENCES

1. A.E. Scheidegger, The Physics of Flow through porous Media. *University of Toronto Press 1974*, 3rd edition (1974)
2. T. G. Gutowski, Z. Cai, S. Bauer, D. Boucher, J. Kingery, and S. Wineman, Consolidation Experiments for Laminate Composites. *Journal of Composite Materials*, **21**, 650 - 669 (1987)
3. H. Bijsterbosch, R. J. Gaymans, Impregnation of Glass Rovings with a Polyamide Melt. Part I: Impregnation Bath. *Composites Manufacturing*, Vol. **4** No. **2**, 85 - 92 (1993)
4. B. P. Van West, R. B. Pipes, and S. G. Advani, The Consolidation of Commingled Thermoplastic Fabrics. *Polymer Composites*, Vol. **12** No. **6**, 417 - 427 (1991)
5. H. Hamada, Z.-I. Maekawa, N. Ikegawa, and T. Matsuo, Influence of the Impregnating Property on Mechanical Properties of Commingled Yarn Composites. *Polymer Composites*, Vol. **14** No. **4**, 308 - 313 (1993)
6. E. J. Jun, T. W. Kim, M. K. Um, W. I. Lee, Effects of Pressure on the Impregnation of Thermoplastic Resin into a Unidirectional Fiber Bundle. *Advancing in Polymer Technology* Vol. **9** No. **4**, 275 - 279 (1989)
7. L. Ye, V. Klinkmüller, K. Friedrich, Impregnation and Consolidation in Composites Made of GF/PP Powder Impregnated Bundles. *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Material*, **5**, 32 - 48 (1992)
8. A. Vodermayr J. C. Kaerger, and G. Hinrichsen, Manufacture of High Performance Fibre-Reinforced Thermoplastics by Aqueous Powder Impregnation. *Composites Manufacturing*, Vol. **4** No. **3**, 123 - 132 (1993)
9. V. Klinkmüller, M.-K. Um, M. Steffens, K. Friedrich, B.-S. Kim, A New Model for Impregnation Mechanisms in Various GF / PP Commingled Yarns. *Applied Composite Materials*, to be published (1995)
10. Saint-John, Vetrotex: Private Communication 1994
11. B. Lauke, K. Schneider, K. Friedrich, Interlaminar Shear Strength Measurements of Thin Composite Rings Fabricated by Filament Winding. *Proceeding of 5th European Conference of Composite Materials, ECCM 5*, 7 - 10 April 1992, Bordeaux, France, EACM-Publication, 313 - 324 (1992)

MANUFACTURING
